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Research Article

**STUDY TO DETERMINE THE CELIAC DISEASE
PREVALENCE IN ADOLESCENTS AND CHILDREN HAVING
TYPE I DIABETES MELLITUS**¹Muhammad Junaid Aleem, ¹Asma Mahmood, ²Parnia Ansari¹Lahore General Hospital, Lahore, ²WMO, RHC Luddan Vehari**Article Received:** October 2019 **Accepted:** November 2019 **Published:** December 2019**Abstract:**

Introduction: While the relationship between celiac disease (CD) and type 1 diabetes mellitus (T1DM) is well known, there is a lack of published data on this association in our region. The purpose of this study was to establish the prevalence of CD in our hospital's Department of Pediatrics in a group of children with type 1 DM undergoing treatment.

Methods: 87 patients (43 male and 44 female) with type 1 diabetes were selected. They ranged in age from 2-18. A group of eighty-seven healthy unrelated boys and girls matched for gender and age were taken as controls. All were screened for the celiac disease manifestations. Anti-tissue transglutaminase (anti-tTG) IgA was measured in blood collected from these patients. Patients with anti-tTG IgA positive underwent duodenal biopsy. Biopsy samples were obtained through an endoscopy procedure. Biopsy specimens were evaluated and CD was diagnosed when complete or partial atrophy of villi, lymphocytic infiltration, and crypt hypertrophy was observed as per the latest criteria of ESPGHAN

Results: The celiac disease incidence in diabetic patients was found to be 3.4%, which was significantly higher than healthy controls. Females had a higher frequency of anti tTG IgA positivity than males. T1DM patients with CD were younger, had a shorter height, less weight and worsened glycemic control ($p < 0.05$). We could not demonstrate a significant relationship between anti-TTG IgA positivity and the duration of diabetes. The results show that positive anti tTG IgA is a good immunity marker for use in celiac studies and that such tests are justified in type I diabetes patients irrespective of the duration of diabetes.

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INTRODUCTION:

Type 1 diabetes or IDDM is an autoimmune disorder in which T cells destroy the pancreatic beta cells. Celiac disease (CD) is a heterogeneous disorder of gluten-sensitive pathological enteropathy. The pathogenesis of the disease is not clear and is believed to be autoimmune. It also involves genetic and environmental influences. In the CD development, Gluten is considered as a trigger molecule. The occurrence of several antibodies (anti-tissue transglutaminase, anti endomysial, antigliadin, anti-reticulon and others) is suggestive of CD. A confirmed diagnosis is based on histological examination of obtained samples from the small bowel. T1DM and CD occur together more frequently than would be expected by chance alone. The prevalence of the coeliac disease among patients with T1DM has been estimated as being between 1–10%. A large UK based study estimated the prevalence among children and adolescents to be 4.8%. [5] The first serological tests for screening CD among the general population employed anti-gliadin antibodies (AGA). In general, and in diabetic population in particular, they were not reliable. The anti-transglutaminase Ab measurement, on the other hand, showed high specificity and sensitivity (100%) (Except for patients with IgA deficiency).

The aim was to determine the prevalence of CD using anti-TTG IgA serology and tissue diagnosis in a cohort of young T1DM patients presenting to us.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This study was held in the Pediatric Medical Unit of Lahore General Hospital, for one-year, from May 2018 to May 2019. 87 patients (43 males and 44 females) were selected for the study. They had type 1 DM and their age range was 2-18 years. The median age was 11.7 ± 4.5 . The diabetes was diagnosed according to the World Health Organization (WHO) criteria. Patients had hyperglycemia and 48.9% had shown signs of ketoacidosis or loss of consciousness as the first presentation of the disease.

Controls:

87 children constituted the control group with an age range of 3-18.5 years. The median age was 11.1 ± 3.9 years. 43 were female and 44 males. No control subjects revealed any symptoms compatible with CD and none were growth retarded. Nobody had a positive family history of CD or Type I diabetes. Age, gender, diabetes onset, weight and height were documented in a series of questionnaires and were answered by both patients and controls.

METHODS:

After ruling out the deficiency of IgA in all patients, anti tTG IgA positivity was established as a CD detection test. Serum glucose and glycosylated Hemoglobin (HbA1c) in diabetic patients were measured.

Intestinal biopsy

Intestinal biopsy was performed in people with anti tTG IgA positivity. Endoscopic duodenal biopsies were preserved and histologically scrutinized by a specialist pathologist.

Diagnosis of celiac disease

In the intestinal mucosa, the CD was diagnosed as complete or partial atrophied, lymphocytic infiltration and crypt hypertrophy by the latest criteria of ESPGHAN.

Statistical analysis

All outcomes are accessible as mean $\pm$ Standard Deviation (SD). For comparison the Student's t-test was used between groups. Less than 5% of the P-value was taken statistically significant.

RESULTS:

Of 87 type I diabetes patients 3 (3.4%) had a positive anti tTG IgA. Anti tTG IgA wasn't detected in the control group. There was no IgA deficiency in patients and control. Three patients who were anti tTG IgA positive, all were confirmed by histology to have CD. Patients tested positive for CD did not show any symptoms of CD in the first interview. CD and diabetes measurements were compared in the table after about 6 months. The average age of patients with diabetes having CD was 7.2 ± 2 years.

Table 1. Clinical characteristics and biochemical measurements in diabetics with and without celiac disease.

	Diabetics without CD (n = 84)	Diabetics with CD (n = 3)
Sex (F/M)	42/42	2/1 *
Age (y)	12.2±3.2	7.2±2.1 *
Age at diabetes onset (y)	7.8 ±3.4	3.1±1.6 *
Weight SDS (kg)	-1.2±0.82	-2.6±0.96 *
Height SDS (cm)	-2.1±1.1	-3.4±1.24*
HbA1c	8.9±1.4	11.25±0.75 *
Serum glucose (mg/dL)	185±41	267±34 *

Results are presented as mean ± SD * statistically significant between diabetics with and without CD. (SDS: Standard deviation score; HbA1c: glycosylated Hemoglobin)

DISCUSSION:

The incidence of celiac disease in diabetes ranged from 0.61% to 7.8% in many studies. More recently, the sensitive screening method shows that the incidence of CD is between 2.9% and 16.02%. In our study, 87 children had type 1 diabetes and three subjects met modified ESPGHAN criteria for CD (3.5% patients). This high variability in study results can be explained by use Anti Gliadin Ab (AGA) to screen coeliac disease in preliminary studies. AGA is not reliable, as only a small percentage of isolated patients with a positive AGA result, show pathological mucosa. A high variability in incidence of CD in type 1 DM may also be due to differences in ethnicity, groups, geographical regions and population size in each study. CD prevalence was significant in our study. At the onset of diabetes, the positivity of the antibody type EMA IgA or anti-tTG IgA is seen in about 60 percent of Type 1 DM CD patients. Such cases, though, are not regularly screened, and identification can be overlooked. Antibody positivity occurs typically a few years after the initiation of diabetes in the remaining 40 percent of cases, and even cases of asymptomatic, advanced stage type 1 DM should be screened for CD⁷. Compared to diabetic patients without CD, height and weight SDS, and glycemic control were significantly lower in T1DM with CD ($p < 0.05$). Diabetic patients with CD were much younger. Increased incidence of CD in patients with diabetes is explained by autoimmune nature of both diseases. It has been suggested, based on previous research, that one of the reasons for the increased incidence of CD in patients with type 1 DM is that these diseases share common genotypes of HLA. HLA genotypes with the highest type 1 DM risk, i.e. DQ2, and DQ8, are present in 90% of CD patients and 8-

10% of CD patients. Like most of previously done studies, we could not demonstrate a significant relationship between CD duration and diabetes. Some authors suggest that the most powerful tool currently available for detecting CD in children older than 2 years is the detection of CD-associated antibodies. A gluten-free diet for asymptomatic patients not only improves general well-being but also improves patient control and blood glucose levels and prevents complications, namely; malnutrition, lack of growth, delayed sexual maturation, osteoporosis, infertility and bowel cancer.

CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, anti-tTG IgA measurement in patients with type 1 DM helped select the appropriate patient for duodenal biopsy. Such findings indicate that the prevalence of CD in children with type 1 DM is higher than in the general population and suggest that regular screenings for children and adolescents with diabetes be recommended ensuring early diagnosis and treatment of CD.

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